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IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY OF JUSTIFICATION OF DESIGN DECISIONS FOR CREATING AN IMAGE VIDEO

The object of research is the process of substantiating design decisions for creating an image video at the pre-production stage. An insufficiently thought-out image video can cause a negative effect that is destructive for the image of the advertised subject. Therefore, every decision made when creating an image video at the pre-production stage must be substantiated on the basis of a multidimensional analysis.

In this study, the content of the traditional stages of the pre-production stage has been improved by taking into account the specifics of the image video, as well as by using the questionnaire method:

- *the image of the advertised entity is considered as a system consisting of a set of specific qualitative characteristics of the relevant person or organization;*
- *the main characteristics of the video being developed are determined by the results of a survey of the target audience.*

The result of the study was an improved methodology for substantiating design decisions for creating an image video, which features:

- 1) *justification of the list of components of the customer's image that need to be advertised;*
- 2) *application of the questionnaire method to determine the main characteristics of the video being developed, such as: type of video, graphic style, color scheme, duration, prevailing ways of presenting information.*

The proposed methodology is concretized to substantiate decisions in the process of creating an image video of an educational program with a dual form of training. The components of the image of the educational program that need to be advertised in the video are determined based on the results of a survey of applicants and students. Expert assessment was carried out using the ranking method. When processing the results of the questionnaire, a difference was revealed in the judgments of different groups of respondents, which became the basis for setting the task of advertising several components of the image of the educational program.

The use of the proposed methodology allows making more informed decisions regarding the content and form of an image video, which will contribute to the establishment of effective relationships between the advertised subject and its stakeholders.

Keywords: *pre-production stage, image video, image components, video parameters, video advertising of an educational program, questionnaire method.*

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1. Introduction

A person sees the world around it through the prism of its mental models. Mental models are a simplified reflection of reality, which is formed in a person on the basis of its experience and «common sense». Each mental model is a person's idea of an object or a subject with which it interacts. The mental models of the organization, which were formed in those who interact with it, determine the image of this subject.

The image of an economic entity (person, group of persons or organization) plays a key role in establishing the relationship of this entity with its stakeholders, counterparties.

It is the image that forms the basis for making decisions by stakeholders on interaction with this subject. In terms of content, the subject's image is its holistic image (relatively stable, emotionally colored) in the eyes of stakeholders. This is a general idea (a set of beliefs and feelings) that has developed in stakeholders about the subject [1]. The image replaces the real subject in the imagination of stakeholders in communication. The image of the subject is formed, first of all, on the basis of the results of the interaction of stakeholders with this subject. The stakeholders have ideas about the quality and efficiency of the subject's work, the conscientiousness and qualifications of its representatives,

the modernity and reliability of technological processes. But stakeholders' own experience is not the only factor in shaping the image of an economic entity. The image of a subject in the eyes of stakeholders is influenced by information about it from various sources: reviews of other persons, media reports, advertising. A specialized tool for image formation is image advertising aimed at creating a holistic and recognizable image of a person or organization. A separate type of image advertising is an image video. Today, when most people get information online, it is video that is becoming one of the most effective types of advertising. An image video can:

- increase brand awareness;
- demonstrate the unique characteristics and advantages of the organization;
- convey corporate values to the target audience;
- separate the advertised subject from competitors;
- convince the audience that the organization's activities are beneficial to society;
- form positive associations associated with the advertised subject.

But poorly thought-out image advertising can backfire, damaging the image of an individual or organization. Therefore, all decisions regarding the characteristics of the image video must be carefully justified.

The process of creating videos consists of three stages: pre-production, production, post-production. Design decisions that determine the content and form of a video are made at the pre-production stage. The main method for generating decisions at this stage is usually brainstorming [2, 3]. Justification of decisions is based on the application of general recommendations of experts [3–5]. But this approach does not take into account the peculiarities of the tasks and conditions for creating a specific video, the preferences of its potential viewers. This problem determined the object and purpose of the study.

So, *the object of research* is the process of substantiating design decisions for creating an image video at the Pre-production stage. *The aim of the study* is to improve the methodology for substantiating design decisions for creating an image video at the Pre-production stage due to the specificity of the type of video in question and the application of the questionnaire method.

2. Methods of research

The traditional pre-production process includes the following steps:

- definition of the purpose of the video;
- development of the concept of the video;
- writing a script with the requirements for the video [6, 7].

In this study, the content of the traditional stages of pre-production has been improved on the basis of taking into account the specifics of the image video, as well as through the use of the questionnaire method:

- the image of the advertised entity is considered as a system consisting of a set of specific qualitative characteristics of the relevant person or organization;
- the main characteristics of the video being developed are determined by the results of a survey of the target audience.

3. Research results and discussion

At the pre-production stage, important design decisions are made that determine the idea, script and video sequence

of the video, which is being developed. Errors at this stage of work are critical. Therefore, each decision that is made at the pre-production stage must be justified on the basis of a bug-aspect analysis, in particular, using a questionnaire survey of representatives of the target audience.

Based on the results of the analysis of the content of the pre-production stage, let's formulate a methodology for substantiating design decisions for creating an image video. As the main means of substantiating decisions in this methodology, let's use a questionnaire survey of the target audience to determine the main characteristics of the video being developed. The proposed technique involves the following stages:

1. *Setting a goal.*

The purpose of the image video is to form a certain image of the customer (that is, the organization or person being advertised) among viewers (representatives of the target audience).

2. *Definition of additional tasks of the image video.*

An additional task of an image video can be, for example:

- dissemination of information about the advertised entity;
- increasing traffic to the site of the advertised entity;
- increasing the attendance of a certain event organized by the advertised entity.

3. *Determination of the list of components of the customer's image that need to be advertised.*

Image, by definition, is a holistic image of the subject; it is an integral system of ideas about this subject in the eyes of its stakeholders. The consistency of the image can be understood by comparing it with the close concept of «reputation» [8–10]. «Reputation is like a black and white photograph: it ranges from black (negative reputation) to white (positive reputation) ... The image is like a bright color image: thousands of shades of color create a coherent image of the company. The image is unique and inimitable, no other company in the world has a similar one ... This is a distinctive feature of the two concepts, that is, several companies can have an equally positive or negative reputation, evaluated in monetary terms, but the image of each is unique and inimitable as a genetic code» [8].

Based on the foregoing, in order to determine the advertised image of the subject, it is necessary to determine the components of this image. Examples of the components of an organization's image: academic performance; initiative; high quality of work; creativity; use of modern technologies; friendly attitude towards clients and partners; low prices.

Justification of the list of components of the customer's image that need to be advertised should be based, on the one hand, on the results of a survey of the target audience, on the other hand, on the results of the analysis of the customer's activities.

Representatives of the target audience should be asked a question of the following type: «Select the most significant criteria for choosing an organization or a person providing the specified services». Examples of answer options: high quality; low price; creativity; conscientious performance of duties.

Further, among the components of the image that are in demand on the part of the target audience, those components are selected that correspond to the advertised subject.

4. *Determination of the main parameters of the video and the preparation of technical specifications.*

The main parameters of the video are given in Table 1.

Table 1

The main parameters of the video

Video parameters	Alternative parameter values
Video type	Graphic; documentary (interview, reportage) staged (fiction, without actors, pseudo-documentary)
Graphic style	Flat design; high tech; cyberpunk; grunge, etc.
Color spectrum	Black and white; monochrome; multicolored
Duration	Up to 1 minute; more than 1 minute
Dominant ways of presenting information	Text; voice acting; graphics

4.1. Determination of the type and graphic style of the video.

The type of video, graphic style and color scheme should be chosen in such a way as to highlight the selected image components that need to be advertised.

To identify the relationship between the specified parameters of the video and the components of the image that is formed among viewers, representatives of the target audience can be asked questions of the following type:

- «Choose which image video is more credible in choosing the organization/person providing the specified services (answer options: based on documentary filming and interviews; based on modern graphics with presentation of text information; based on acting)».
- «What graphic style of the video (from the listed ones) contributes to the fact that the advertised organization/person will be perceived as advanced in terms of the latest technologies?»
- «What graphic style of the video (from the listed ones) will contribute to the fact that the advertised organization/people will be perceived as a leader in product quality?»

4.2. Determination of the dominant ways of presenting information in the video.

The duration of the video and the dominant ways of presenting information should be selected in such a way as to ensure a high efficiency of perception by viewers of the information given in the video.

To identify the relationship between the specified parameters of a video and the effectiveness of its perception by viewers, representatives of the target audience can be asked questions of the following type:

- «What is the duration of the image video that will allow to comfortably receive its information? (Answer options: up to 1 minute; more than 1 minute)».
- «What is the most convenient way of presenting information about the advertised organization/person in the video for perception? (Answer options: in the form of text, in the form of voice acting; in the form of a graph – diagrams and illustrations)».

5. *Writing a script taking into account the specified parameters of the video (in this case, the text of the plot is supplemented with a description of the video sequence).*

The result of this stage is the director's script. The director's script is not just a story, but actually a preliminary work plan. It is drawn up in the form of a structured document (for example, a table) with an indication of all the necessary components of each scene (sound, props in the frame, actor, text on the screen, etc.).

An example of concretizing the technique. Let's concretize the proposed methodology for substantiating design decisions for creating an image video of an educational

and professional program (EPP) of a higher educational institution with a dual form of education.

1. *Setting a goal.*

The purpose of the planned to develop an image video is to form a given image of the educational program in the dual form of education among applicants, which is proposed by a specific educational institution.

2. *Definition of additional tasks of the image video.*

Additional tasks of the image video can be:

- informing applicants that the advertised educational program has a dual form of training;
- informing applicants about what dual training is, and what advantages it gives the student.

3. *Determination of the list of components of the image of the educational program that need to be advertised.*

In order to determine the components of the image of the educational program, it is advisable to conduct a questionnaire survey among representatives of the target audience (i. e. applicants), during which to offer the following question:

«Rank by importance is the characteristics of the educational program of a higher educational institution:

- proximity of the content of the educational program to my interests;
- high demand for graduates of this educational program in the labor market;
- high salaries of graduates of this educational program;
- high positions of graduates of this educational program of a particular university;
- high quality of teaching disciplines for this educational program in a particular higher educational institution;
- achievements of teachers in the field of science;
- university ranking among the country's universities;
- good material base of training;
- comfortable learning conditions;
- modern technical support for classes;
- availability of an individual approach;
- practical orientation of training and the availability of training opportunities in the workplace (the presence of a dual form of training);
- availability of internship opportunities while studying».

As an example of the implementation of the proposed approach to identify the components of the image of the educational program of the university, let's present the results of a study conducted by a master's student at the Kharkiv National University of Economics (Ukraine) [11, 12]. The survey covered a sample of 83 respondents – university entrants, students and alumni. Expert assessment was carried out using the ranking method.

The respondents were given the following task: «Rank the following criteria for choosing an educational and professional program and place of study (for this, set each criterion to a rank from 1 to 6, where 1 is the most important criterion).

Criteria options:

- 1) proximity of the content of professional activity to my interests;
- 2) success of graduates in this specialty; demand for this specialty in the labor market and average wages;
- 3) quality of teaching;
- 4) achievement of teachers in the field of science;
- 5) rating of the university among the universities of Ukraine;
- 6) learning conditions».

The calculation of the sum of the ranks given by the respondents for each criterion showed that the criterion

«high quality of teaching» received the lowest sum of ranks, that is, this criterion is the most important for the majority of the respondents. But when checking the consistency of the opinions of the respondents, it turned out that the coefficient of concordance is 0.43, which indicates a low degree of consistency of judgments. Therefore, it was decided to process the judgments of the respondents not together, but in groups. The following groups of persons were identified among the respondents: applicants (8 people), bachelors of 1–2 years (31 people); bachelors of 3–4 years (21 people); masters (13 people) and graduates (10 people). This made it possible to take into account the difference in the judgments of different groups of respondents. The results of the survey by groups of respondents are shown in Table 2. Coefficients of concordance, calculated for the groups, showed a sufficient level of consistency of judgments within the formed groups.

Table 2

Results of a survey of various groups of respondents in order to identify the most important criteria for choosing an educational and professional program and a place of study

Groups of respondents	The most important criterion	Criterion no. 2	Criterion no. 3
Applicants	The success of graduates in this speciality	Ranking of the university among the universities of Ukraine	The proximity of the content of professional activity to my interests
Bachelors of 1–2 courses	High quality teaching	The success of graduates in this speciality	Achievements of teachers in the field of science
Bachelors of 3–4 years	Ranking of the university among the universities of Ukraine	High quality teaching	The success of graduates in this speciality
Masters	The success of graduates in this speciality	The proximity of the content of professional activity to my interests	High quality teaching
Graduates	The success of graduates in this speciality	The proximity of the content of professional activity to my interests	High quality teaching

As is possible to see from the Table 2, different groups of respondents chose different criteria for evaluating the educational and professional program. But the presence of a difference in the judgments of different groups of respondents is not a big problem, since the video can advertise several components of the image of the educational and professional program (in particular, the high quality of teaching, and the success of graduates in professional activities).

4. Determination of the main parameters of the video and the preparation of technical specifications.

At this stage, among other things, it is important to identify such characteristics of the video that will convey the advantages of the dual form of education within the educational and professional program. For example, respondents may be asked a question of this type: «Choose what type of image video will better convey the benefits of the dual form of education to the audience? Answer options: based on documentary filming and interviews; based on modern graphics with the presentation of textual information; based on acting».

5. Writing a script taking into account the specified parameters of the video.

At this stage, the script of the video is formed. Among other things, at this stage it is advisable to choose creative

techniques and special effects that will contribute to the advertising of the dual form of education within the EPP framework.

4. Conclusions

The study improved the methodology for substantiating design decisions for creating an image video at the pre-production stage. The features of the proposed technique are:

1) justification of the list of components of the customer's image that need to be advertised;

2) application of the questionnaire method to determine the main characteristics of the video being developed (such as the type of video, graphic style, color scheme, duration, prevailing ways of presenting information).

These features of the methodology allow making more informed decisions regarding the content and form of an image video, which will contribute to the establishment of effective relationships between the advertised subject and its stakeholders.

The obtained results of the research will be of interest to specialists of agencies and video production studios, as well as to a wide range of people involved in the process of creating image videos.

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